

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Okello****FIRST NAME: Richard****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 9%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Kate L. Turabian, research is?

- A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question the researcher and others want to solve.¹**
- Looking for answers to questions.
- Choosing a new phone.
- Discovering the origin of life.

2. Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of an abstract in a dissertation?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

Helps the reader decide whether the dissertation research is relevant enough (to his or her study).²

Helps the reader know whether the methods used in the study are reliable.

Helps the reader know whether the data were well analysed.

Helps the reader understand the background of the study.

3. According to Sampson, a statement of the problem is?

A succinct statement of the dilemma the research questions intend to resolve.³

A statement that justifies the student's time and financial resources that need to be devoted to the research

A statement that describes the nature of the specific differences or relationships among variables that will be tested in the dissertation research

A statement that provides a succinct explanation of the variables

4. What are the five elements of a research argument?

Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgement and response, and warrant.⁴

Claim, reason, question, evidence, and warrant

Objectives, reason, evidence, warrant, and response

Reason, evidence, acknowledgement, response, and warrant

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017), 26.

³ Ibid., 28.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 58.

5. Which of the following statements best describes an academic essay?
- A non-fictional writing produced as part of academic work.⁵**
 - An essay describing an object with a sentiment value for the writer.
 - An essay that describes an experience where the writer learned something.
 - An essay that is written for purposes of entertainment.
6. Which of the following statements is true about the critical analysis of the literature?
- It explains the content and methodology gaps identified during the literature review.⁶**
 - Explains the sources consulted in the dissertation research.
 - Gives a summary of the literature review
 - Shows the scope of the research
7. To avoid plagiarism, it is essential to paraphrase appropriately. A good paraphrase should have all of the following qualities except?
- The writing style you use to express the author's ideas should be the same as the style the author used.⁷**
 - Must be your own words.
 - The language used should not resemble the words of the author.
 - You should not just change a few words and rearrange the sentence structure.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 32.

⁷ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1*, 36.

8. When reviewing a paper, it is advisable to?
- Revise from whole to part.⁸**
 - Revise from part to whole
 - Revise soft copy
 - Revise the overall organisation and sections only
9. Which of the following best describes the WHO style?
- Use the right names for WHO, its Member States and partners, and treat text correctly and consistently.⁹**
 - When listing the WHO Member States, do not list them in alphabetical order
 - Do not call partners and other organisations the names they have chosen if it conflicts with WHO styles.
 - Use only US English in all information products.
10. The WHO is committed to working towards equality between all people. To ensure this is reflected in all its information products, which of the following should writers do?
- Refer to age, disability status, racial or cultural background, sex and sexual orientation only when directly relevant to the subject, using adjectives rather than nouns.¹⁰**

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 106.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 1.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 55.

- Older people can be referred to as frail, incapable of independence but not a burden on society
- Young people can be referred to as inexperienced and rebellious but not immature
- Hide or ignore but do not downgrade the relevance of disability

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.